

The innovative design of carbon dots on polymer texture for highly selective detection of amino compounds

Moorthy Maruthapandi¹, Arulappan Durairaj², Arumugam Saravanan², John H.T. Luong³, Aristides Bakandritsos^{1,4}, Aharon Gedanken², and Radek Zboril^{1,4}

¹*Nanotechnology Centre, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic*

²*Department of Chemistry, Bar-Ilan Institute for Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials, Bar-Ilan University, Ramat-Gan 52900, Israel*

³*School of Chemistry, University College Cork, Cork T12 YN60, Ireland*

⁴*Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute, Palacký University Olomouc, Šlechtitelů 27, Olomouc, 783 71, Czech Republic*

* Corresponding authors: radek.zboril@upol.cz and gedanken@mail.biu.ac.il

Abstract

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are of growing concern due to their toxicity and environmental impact. Their facile detection is thus of a high importance but still challenging because they are unreactive and often present at very low concentrations. Developing sensing schemes for VOCs based on low-cost, sensitive, selective, and user-friendly methods is therefore crucial for environmental monitoring. To address these issues, we herein developed polymer supported carbon dots (CDs) by reacting tetraminobenzene with 2,4,6-trichlorophenyl oxalate using a simple reflux method. Owing to the selection of precursors, polymer supported fluorescent carbon dots (P-CDs) were grown decorating the synthesized polymeric spheres. The P-CDs composites were highly stable, and their fluorescence was drastically quenched by several VOC analytes (ethanolamine, diethanolamine, triethanolamine, and ammonia) due to the rich surface functional groups that could effectively and selectively interact with amines. The polymer component contributed to ascribing excellent photophysical and chemical stability, which is

valuable particularly for sensing in complex matrices. As a result, the developed P-CDs exhibited superior properties when applied as VOC sensors, including high selectivity for several amines but not for other organic species, fast response, and very high stability, while offering a simple detection method, and minimum sample pre-treatment. The P-CD design has extended potential for diverse sensing applications, including, for instance, control of prohibited transport of chemicals and post-toxic analysis.

Graphical Abstract

1. Introduction

Aliphatic and aromatic volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are organic molecules with comparatively high vapor pressure, consequently, they spread easily in the natural and working environment. The VOCs are often toxic to organisms and human exposure can cause serious respiratory diseases [1]. Several VOCs have also been linked to environmental degradation. VOC analysis has diverse applications in food, agriculture, healthcare, environmental monitoring, and

other fields [2,3]. The detection of VOCs is challenging because most VOCs are unreactive and often are present in low concentrations, lower than the detection limit of various known analytical methods [4]. Developing sensing schemes for VOCs is a crucial challenge for air monitoring applications. Current analytical methods include mass spectrometry, ion flow tube mass spectrometry, quartz crystal microbalance, surface acoustic wave sensing, and chemosensing. Mass spectrometry connected with gas chromatography (GC-MS) can identify thousands of unknown and known VOCs [1]. Nevertheless, GC-MS is expensive, energy/time consuming, and requires considerable technical skill. Despite the broad variety of sensing techniques, present technologies face challenges for real, easy-to-apply VOC detection, requiring expensive devices, complex synthetic approaches of the transduction materials, and lack of selectivity/sensitivity [5,6]. The ideal VOC detector must have high analytical performance in terms of selectivity, stability, reproducibility, fast response, recovery, and minimal sample pre-treatment [7,8].

These prerequisites have been pursued by the development of carbon nanomaterials, facilitating the development of fluorescence sensing tools and devices [9,10]. Carbon dots (CDs) with an average diameter of less than 10 nm have a great potential in many fields such as biotechnology, energy, optoelectronics, and nanomedicine due to their excellent water solubility, biocompatibility, rich chemical, and photoluminescence properties [11]. The CDs can be prepared by diverse simple and cost-effective approaches including bottom-up synthesis, hydrothermal, and microwave-assisted carbonization. Furthermore, the molecular precursors of CDs are usually based on inexpensive sources originating from biomass derived small molecules or nature organic compounds, eliminating the need for high-cost or critical raw materials [12,13]. Interaction of CDs with VOCs can result in changes in the fluorescent emission, such as fluorescence enhancement, fluorescence quenching, emission peak shift, and resonance energy transfer, which can typically

depend upon the type of the electronic interactions between the CDs and VOCs [14]. The CDs offer variable and high flexibility in their functions via their rich chemistry and corresponding properties, such as lifetime, excitation and emission, anisotropy, fluorescence decay, and quantum yield [15].

However, there are also challenges for the effective application of CDs. For instance, interparticle π - π interactions and resonance energy transfer can significantly compromise the fluorescence intensity. Furthermore, the reusability of the ultrasmall CDs is challenging because they are very difficult to separate [16,17]. Recently, the development of appropriate supports for the immobilization of carbon dots has been demonstrated as a promising method to increase the stability of CDs [18]. Such strategies may increase the stability of the synthesized CDs by functioning in a mutually beneficial relationship, maintaining the distance between the individual CDs and avoiding their aggregation [19]. Combining such features with reactive and selective surface chemistry for VOC detection remains of high importance in the field.

This work demonstrates a simple method for the synthesis of polymer embedded fluorescence carbon dots (P-CDs) with enhanced thermal, mechanical, and optical properties. P-CDs composite contains carbon dots decorating the microspheres synthesized from the mild carbonization of a fluorescent non-conjugated polymer by reacting 1,2,4,5-benzenetetramine tetrahydrochloride (BTA) with 2,4,6-trichlorophenyl oxalate at 210 °C for 2 h by a simple reflux method. The P-CDs were highly stable, while their photophysical properties were intact for at least three months. Endowed with a rich surface of functional groups they could effectively and selectively interact with several amine VOC analytes, leading to strong fluorescence quenching in the presence of ethanolamine (EA), diethanolamine (DEA), triethanolamine (TEA), and ammonium hydroxide

(NH₄-OH). The effectiveness of the P-CDs lies on the selective, rapid, and sensitive detection of VOCs, which can be practically exploited in safety and monitoring platforms for amines.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Solvents and reagents such as bis(2,4,6-trichlorophenyl) oxalate (TCPO), benzene tetramine hydrochloride (BTA), polyphosphoric acid (PPA), diethanolamine (HN(CH₂CH₂OH)₂ DEA), ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH), acetonitrile (MeCN), ethanol (EtOH), methanol (MeOH), diethylene glycol (DEG), acetone (Ace), ethyl acetate (EtOAc), trichloroacetic acid (TCA), 2-propanol (2-PrOH), dioxane (Diox), hexane (Hex), t-butanol, toluene, dimethylformamide (DMF), tetrahydrofuran (THF), dimethylacetamide (DMA), triethyleneglycol (TEG), chloroform (Chl) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Solvents Ethylolamine (HO(CH₂)₂NH₂, EA) and triethanolamine (N(CH₂CH₂OH)₃ TEA) were purchased from Acros organics and Fisher scientific, Israel.

2.2. Preparation of P-CDs

P-CDs were synthesized by a simple one-step reflux method. 3 mmol of TCPO (0.13 g), 5.2 mmol of benzene tetramine hydrochloride (0.15 g), and polyphosphoric acid (6 mL) was added to a round bottom flask and heated at 210 °C for 2 h. The resulting brownish-black mixture was then kept at 160 °C for 2 days and cooled down at room temperature. Deionized water (500 mL) was then added to the resulting liquid and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant

was aqueous P-CDs, and the precipitate was unreacted CDs of the polymer. The CD-decorated polymer was confirmed by HR-TEM, TGA, and solid-state ^{13}C -NMR. The synthetic procedure and the formation of the nanocomposite are illustrated in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of synthesis of P-CDs. NH₂ groups of carbon dots formed from benzene tetramine react with the Cl groups on TCPO, which undergoes polymerization, leading to carbon dots immobilized on a polymeric support.

2.3. Analytical techniques

Microscopic studies of CDs and the CD-coated surface were conducted by transmission electron microscopy (TEM- JEOL-2100, Peabody, MA, USA). A drop of the CDs solution was dropped on the copper grid and dried overnight at 60° C. The P-CDs absorbance was measured using a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 100 Bio Spectrophotometer). The

photoluminescence measurement was obtained using a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 100 Bio Spectrophotometer). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra, ranging from 500 to 4000 cm^{-1} , were analyzed using a Tensor 27 spectrometer (Bruker, Germany). The surface elemental analysis was performed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy on an Nexsaspectrometer XPS (England).

2.3. Fluorescence quantum yield (%) measurement

The quantum yield (%) of P-CDs was measured using quinine sulfate in 0.1M in H_2SO_4 as a standard. The quantum yield was calculated as follows:

$$\varphi_{\text{sample}} = \varphi_{\text{std}} \times \frac{A(\text{sample})}{A(\text{reference})} \times \frac{F(\text{sample})}{F(\text{reference})} \times \frac{\eta(\text{sample})^2}{\eta(\text{reference})^2} \quad (1)$$

where Φ_{std} denotes the known quantum yield of quinine sulfate (54%), A -integrated fluorescence intensity (area under spectrum), F -fluorescence emission intensity, and η is the refractive index of solvent (water: 1.33). Integrated fluorescence intensity vs optical absorbance and integrated area vs optical absorbance of quinine sulfate and P-CDs are given in Fig S1.

2.4. Fluorescence sensing of amines by P-CDs

For fluorescence sensing, 1 mL of P-CDs (150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was mixed with 1 mL of various organic compound solutions (5-100 mM). The PL intensity of P-CDs at 390 nm (Ex.) was measured after a 5 min incubation at room temperature. For selective determination, 1 mL of P-CDs were mixed with 1 mL of amine compounds (10–100 mM) such as EA, DEA, TEA, and NH_3 . The emission spectra were recorded after 10 min of incubation at room temperature. The quenching efficiency was calculated as follows [20].

$$\text{Quenching efficiency} = \left[\frac{I_0 - I}{I_0} \right] 100\%$$

where I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities of P-CDs in the absence and presence of amines.

2.5. Stability of P-CDs

The stability of P-CDs was measured at room temperature over the days. The P-CDs was diluted by DDW to measure the PL intensity and the PL intensity was measured for up to 90 days with 20 days intervals.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microscopic characterization

Representative transmission electron micrographs (TEM) of P-CDs are shown in **Fig. 1 and Fig S2**. The polymer exhibits an irregular shape with CDs well distributed within the matrix, without indication of aggregation (Fig. 1a & Fig. S2). As shown in Fig. 1c, the CDs are spherical and are evenly distributed and firmly attached to the polymer matrix. The corresponding cumulative particle size histogram suggested that the polymer nanospheres had diameters ranging from ~12-20 nm, while CDs had 3-5 nm diameter (Fig. 1b, d). In general, the reaction of a primary amine (R_1-NH_2) with a chloride group (R_2-Cl) results in formation of R_1-NH-R_2 with the liberation of HCl. Thus, the plausible reaction of TCPO with benzene tetramine would form different heterogeneous polymers as one molecule of TCPO could be sandwiched by two benzene tetramine molecules and vice versa [21]. As the grown CDs in presence of benzene tetramine may also

express surface amino groups, these NH_2 groups of CDs may also react with the Cl groups of TCPO forming covalent CD's polymer composites, as shown in Scheme 1.

Figure 1. (a, b) HR-TEM image and size distribution of polymeric particles in P-CDs. (c, d) HR-TEM image and size distribution of carbon dots in P-CDs.

3.2 Optical and chemical characterization of P-CDs

The UV absorbance spectra of P-CDs (Fig. 2a) show two absorbance peaks at 230 nm is assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the aromatic C=C bonds domain and the peak around 263 nm is attributed to the $n-\pi^*$ transition of the C=O/amine groups in the P-CDs, respectively [22]. The

inset of Fig. 2a shows the P-CDs solution in daylight and their bright blue color emission under UV light (365 nm). The fluorescence spectra of the P-CDs in aqueous solution measured with various excitation wavelengths are displayed in Fig. 2b. Upon changing the excitation wavelength from 340 nm to 400 nm, the fluorescence intensity increased. The maximum fluorescence intensity was observed at 468 nm when P-CDs were excited at 390 nm. The fluorescence intensity of P-CDs is relatively high while bearing C–OH, C=O, C–N, and C–Cl groups, as discussed in the following [11]. The quantum yield (QY) of P-CDs was determined to be as high as 51.6% in water, using as reference the known QY of quinine sulfate (54%) in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ (Fig. S1).

Figure 2. (a) UV-absorption spectrum and (b) fluorescence spectrum of P-CDs. Inset in panel a) demonstrates photographs of P-CDs solution under daylight (DL) and UV-light (UV) at 365 nm.

The elemental composition of the polymer-supported carbon dots was determined with XPS. The P-CDs consist of carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, and chlorine with atomic ratios of 63.16, 22.43, 3.1, and 11.27, respectively (Fig. S3). The presence of nitrogen and chlorine reflects the chemical functionalization of CDs with amino groups and their embedding in the Cl-containing polymer matrix, respectively. The high-resolution XPS spectra of C 1s exhibited four predominant

components at 284.9, 286.3, 288.6, and 289.4 eV, referred to as the C-C/C=C, C-O/sp² carbon-nitrogen, C=O, and O-C=O functional groups (Fig. 3a) [22]. The deconvolution of high-resolution O1s XPS spectrum showed two components at 532 eV, and 534 eV corresponding to the C-O/O-C-O and C=O functional groups, respectively (Fig. 3b) [23]. The N1s spectrum (Fig. 3c) was deconvoluted into four components assigned to pyridinic N (398.32 eV), pyrrolic-N (399 eV), quaternary-N (399.8 eV), and N-H (401 eV), attesting the presence of nitrogen heteroatoms and amino groups in the structure of graphitic carbon dots[24]. In the Cl2p XPS spectrum (Fig. 3d), the two components at 201 eV and 202.3 eV are attributed to the Cl 2p_{3/2} and Cl 2p_{1/2} core-level binding energies, respectively [25].

Figure 3. High-resolution XPS spectra of P-CDs: (a) C 1 s, (b) O 1 s, (c) N 1s, and (d) Cl 2p.

Based on the TGA thermal analysis, the P-CDs were stable up to 185 °C. They exhibited a small weight loss at 100 °C, which may be due to the elimination of adsorbed water. Additionally, two main events in temperature ranges between 185-275 °C and 276-650 °C were observed. The first decomposition event is due to the depolymerization, decarboxylation, and the loss of O-H, C-H, C=O, C-C, and C-O moieties [26]. The consequent mass loss at 276-650 °C is mainly attributed to the decomposition of the carbonaceous matrix of the P-CDs. As shown in Fig. S4a,

the thermal decomposition of P-CDs is completed with the formation of graphite residue. The oxidative decomposition of graphite begins at 650 °C (20%). Finally, ^{13}C NMR of P-CDs were measured to complete their structural characterization (Fig S4b) The peak 'a' located around 38-50 ppm are due to sp^3 carbon, which are located on the CDs surface, and the peak 'b' at 91-99 ppm is attributed to the aliphatic C-O. The broad polymer peak includes the shoulder peaks between 98-160 ppm, are attributed to the aromatic carbons in the P-CDs. The broad 'd' signal at 198 ppm assigned to the carboxyl groups in the P-CDs surface[27]. In summary, the ^{13}C solid-state NMR confirms the formation of the insoluble polymer composites.

3.3 Selectivity of P-CDs towards amines detection

The prepared P-CDs were further examined for their sensing ability to detect selected organic compounds by quenching of the fluorescence of P-CDs. For the selectivity, the fluorescence intensity of P-CDs was recorded in the presence of various solvents, acids, amines, and alcohols at 470 nm (λ_{em}) at room temperature and after 10 mins incubation. The changed photoluminescence properties of P-CDs after the reaction with different organic reagents or solutes are expressed as the relative change in the PL intensity (I_0-I)/ I_0 . As shown in Fig. 4, substantial fluorescence quenching was observed only in the case of amines (EA, DEA, TEA, NH_4OH , and NH_3 , Figure 4d) in comparison to all other tested organic compounds (Fig. 4a-c).

Figure 4. The changes of fluorescence intensity ratio $(I_o-I)/I_o$ of P-CDs interacting with various organic compounds. Data are provided as a mean \pm S.D, $n=3$.

3.4 Sensitivity of P-CDs towards amines

The sensing properties of P-CDs towards various amines was further evaluated by monitoring the changes in the fluorescence (FL) intensity in the presence of EA, DEA, TEA, and NH₄-OH at different concentrations (10-90 mM). Fig. 5 shows the quenching of the PL intensity of P-CDs in the presence of the target amine compounds. The concentration dependant fluorescence quenching of P-CDs clearly indicates the developing interactions between the P-CDs and the amines and the ability for quantitative sensing. In general, the decline of CDs intensity with the addition of analytes or solutes could be related to out inner-filter effects related to

fluorescence quenching. Almost all amine compounds (analytes) quenched the fluorescence intensity of P-CDs.[28]

Figure 5. Sensitive fluorescence detection of amines by P-CDs. (a) ethanolamine (EA), (b) diethanolamine (DEA), (c) triethylolamine (TEA), and (d) NH₄-OH

Further, we calculated the quenching efficiency using previous methodologies [28] as shown in Fig. 6. The concentration-dependent quenching efficiency was observed for all amine compounds. The quenching efficiency is about 90.1% and 90.9 % for EA and TEA at 40 mM,

while DEA and $\text{NH}_4\text{-OH}$ required 90 mM and 80 mM concentrations to obtain 90.9 and 77.1%, respectively (Fig. 6). The higher selectivity of P-CDs towards EA and TEA leads to greater QE at lower concentrations compared to other analytes. The limit of detection (LOD) was calculated by plotting the linear relationship between the fluorescence ratio I_0/I versus different concentrations of amines (mM) (Fig. S5). The LOD of P-CDs for EA, DEA, TEA, and $\text{NH}_4\text{-OH}$ was determined to be 18.50 mM, 31.08 mM, 29.97 mM, and 29.95 mM, respectively. For comparison the LODs from different types of nanomaterials, composites, and polymers are presented in Table S1. The Table S1 shows that tedious and expensive reagents/precursors have been used for the synthesis of detection probes and sensing of amines; moreover these sensors are responsive only to one specific amine molecule. Interestingly, P-CDs are not only cost-effective and stable but can effectively detect a broad gamut of potentially hazardous amines indicating their high practical applicability.

Figure. 6. The quenching efficiency of P-CDs as a function of amines concentration. (a) ethanolamine, (b) diethanolamine, (c) triethanolamine, and (d) ammonium hydroxide. Data are provided as a mean \pm S.D., n=3.

3.5 Ammonia detection in the real sample of the agriculture soil

Lettuce plants (*Lactuca sativa*) obtained from the Agriculture Research Center in Israel were thoroughly washed with distilled water before being planted. They were then cultivated in a greenhouse alongside a control group (Fig 7). The greenhouse conditions were maintained at 25°C, with each pot containing eight plants. Commercial NPK fertilizer containing various amino

compounds like urea, ammonium nitrate, and ammonium sulfate was used to enhance the plant growth. Specifically, 3.2 g/L of NPK was added to the pots, along with a control containing just the water, and after 10 days, soil samples were collected from each pot and rinsed with 20 mL of distilled water. The resulting water extracts were filtered using Whatman filter paper, purified with a 0.22- μ M filter, and stored in the refrigerator until required. These extracts from the NPK and control pots were later mixed with carbon dots for the detection of ammonia using fluorescence spectroscopy. The LOD of P-CDs for this real sample was determined to be 30.24 mM and relative intensity changes of P-CDs upon adding increasing concentration are given in Fig S6.

The efficacy of NPK fertilizers in enhancing plant growth compared untreated control clearly seen in Figure 7a and well documented in the literature [29]. However, the adverse consequences of NPK overuse, such as soil pollution and ammonia release, underscore the need for detection and remediation strategies. Following this direction, the utilization of P-CDs for ammonia detection in post-lettuce cultivation soil has been explored[30]. Soil filtrates were mixed with carbon dots and subsequently analysed via fluorescence spectroscopy, employing an excitation wavelength of 390 nm. Figure 7b demonstrates a discernible decline in fluorescence intensity with increasing NPK concentration in soil extracts. Conversely, control pot fluorescence intensity remained nearly unchanged corroborating the specificity of the carbon dot-assisted method for highly selective detection of amino compounds in real samples.

Figure 7. Plant cultivation with (a) NPK fertilizer (left) and control without fertilizer (right), and (b) fluorescence detection of amines in NPK-containing agriculture soil.

3.6 Mechanism of P-CDs quenching by various amines and stability of P-CDs

To understand the mechanism of sensing by P-CDs, we have further measured the fluorescence lifetime decays of the P-CDs in the absence and presence of amines by time-correlated single photon counting. Typically, fluorescence quenching can be dynamic or static. In the first case, it is caused by non-radiative energy transfer between the fluorophore and the quencher, leading to a decrease of the fluorescence lifetime of the fluorophore (the P-CDs in this case). In the second case, quenching takes place via the formation of non-radiative dark complexes between the fluorophore and the quencher, and there is no lifetime decay change in this case. [31,32] Figure 8a shows the fluorescence decay curves of the pure P-CDs and P-CDs in the presence of the amines. Clearly, the presence of amines leads to the decrease in the fluorescence lifetime of P-CDs. According to the results summarized in Table S2, P-CDs had an average lifetime of 8.28 ns, which decreased upon addition of EA, DEA, TEA, and $\text{NH}_4\text{-OH}$ to 5.13 ns, 4.78 ns, 5.29 ns, and 4.97 ns, respectively. This suggests that the fluorescence quenching of P-CDs is dominantly caused by a dynamic quenching mechanism between P-CDs and amines. **However, the absorption spectra (Figure S7) exhibit distinct bands for the pure P-CDs at 230 nm and 263**

nm. After the addition of amines to the P-CDs system, subtle shifts and attenuations are observed in both the $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transition peaks. These alterations signify a nuanced interplay of dynamic and static quenching phenomena between the P-CDs and the amine derivatives, elucidating the intricate nature of their molecular interactions [33,34]. The investigation into the photostability of P-CDs entailed subjecting them to a harsh 7200-seconds UV irradiation session under a Xenon (Xe) lamp[35]. Subsequent analysis of the fluorescence spectra unveiled a remarkable preservation, with the P-CDs exhibiting a retention of 97% of their initial fluorescence intensity post-exposure (Figure S8).

Finally, the fluorescence optical stability of the developed P-CDs sensor was measured as this is a crucial parameter for applications in sensorics. The fluorescence stability of P-CDs was measured at room temperature over three months with a 20-day interval. The PL intensity of P-CDs remained stable (Fig. 8b) even for 80 days, offering the superior capability of storage for a long time at room temperature ($\sim 32-37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) thus supporting the practical use for sensing purposes and long-term storage.

Figure 8. (a) Fluorescence lifetime decay of pristine P-CDs and P-CDs in the presence of various amino compounds and (b) fluorescence stability of P-CDs at room temperature for 80 days. Data are provided as a mean \pm S.D., n=3.

3.7 Interference with metal ions

The impact of diverse metals on the detection capability of carbon dots is a significant issue as metal ions are inherent impurities present in real samples. The effect of various metal ions on fluorescence quenching of P-CDs in the presence of ammonia is elucidated in Figure 9 and Figure S9. Primarily, various metal ions (100 mM) were added to the dispersion of P-CDs. The findings revealed a negligible effect of metal ions on the photoluminescence intensity of P-CDs suspension. Then, the fluorescence intensity changes of P-CDs were assessed by mixing 10 mM ammonia solution with 100 mM of metal ions. The addition of ammonia triggered the significant fluorescence quenching of P-CDs for all the studied systems containing various metal ions. These data clearly prove the negligible effect of metal ions on detection capability of P-CDs in sensing of ammonia-based species via the fluorescence quenching.

Figure 9. Effect of metal ions (100 mM) on fluorescence detection of ammonia with P-CDs.

4. Conclusions

We report a simple strategy for embedding carbon dots onto the surface of polymeric nanospheres by a one-step reflux synthesis method, whereby both the carbon dots and the polymeric nanospheres are grown in situ. The prepared P-CDs were thoroughly characterized and found to act as selective fluorescent probes for the detection of amino compounds, owing to their surface chemistry. Notably, the fabricated P-CDs sensors displayed excellent selectivity for amino compounds, including ammonia, but not for VOCs containing other chemical groups. Furthermore, P-CDs showed quite high sensitivity and quantum yield (51.6% in water) along with very high fluorescence stability, which are crucial properties for their practical applicability. The obtained results showcase the significant potential of P-CDs in advanced technologies such as the cost-

effective detection of amine compounds which can be related to sensing of pharmaceuticals, explosives, or food quality monitoring.

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